

Boxing Out Hyper-Masculinity

An EPEMC perspective on masculine and hyper-masculine behaviors with respect to the Mars/Ares/Thor/Hercules motif using Greco-Roman-Nordic examples and discussion of Historical European Martial Arts (brief) and western pugilistic boxing.

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ABSTRACT

Masculinity and Hyper-masculinity are not well understood, or are often referred to pejoratively and unconstructively. By observing the cataclysmic myths and past, the issues of hyper-masculine behavior can be understood as taught and re-affirmed behavioral modes that combine biological response (instinct), physical and chemical law, and mythic understanding. This teaching is preserved and encouraged by both genders and not only males. Solutions to machismo behaviors require looking at cultures which most effectively remembered the cataclysms and evaluating how they understood the Mars-Venus affair c. 1600-1700 BCE.

Key words: *Masculinity - Mars- Venus - Boxing - Martial Arts - Violence Prevention*

Introduction

- I. “Verb: box out (third-person singular simple present boxes out, present participle boxing out, simple past and past participle boxed out)
 - A. (basketball) To position oneself between an opposition player and the basket in anticipation of getting a rebound.
 - B. (transitive, figuratively, by extension) To arrange a situation so as to exclude (someone).”¹
- II. To out-box may also imply to perform better or to push out via competition.
- III. To get out of a box or think outside of the box, to escape a trap, for instance.

These are all the implications the author means in the title. Though the author is male (and thereby derives the authority on male subjects) as a practitioner of Daode² and Zhongyi³ (Chinese medicine), there is a strong proclivity towards harmonization of yin and yang (Taiji⁴) and therefore there will be references to the female/mysterious female contained herein. The author acknowledges that several people wish to escape the polar configurations of nature and social “constructs” derived thereby⁵, in which case consider this treatise as addressing only those who wish instead to understand the impossible-to-define Dao and thereby to harmonize the Taiji⁶.

One other note is that this is not a discussion of “toxic” masculinity, which in Chinese would refer to something more specific, and a pathology of the individual, and yet by broad application of the postmodernist is implicating the entire gender, and so is a gross term. Instead, the use of hyper, meaning above or too much, will be applied, and always in relation to a standard of behavior in conformation not with mores and norms alone but also the law. Gregarious and masculine behavior, such as raucousness and rowdiness, or ideas such as stoicism⁷, cannot therefore on their own by hyper masculine ipso facto. They must be compared in case by case behavior.

Figure 1 - The Taiji & Bagua; credit: astro-fengshui.com

The purpose of this document is to make no excuses for abusive hetero-normative or anglo-masculine (ie, westernized masculinity) behaviors, if they indeed be toxic or criminal, as case by case analysis could reveal. It is instead to focus on the origins of the hyper-masculine behavior, particularly with respect to martiality and violent sport, and the context (potential or real) of the Mars/Ares-Venus/Athena/Diana clash circa 1600 BCE⁸, and the Mars cataclysm circa 600-700 BCE. The use of previous motifs from the Sumo analysis paper⁹, combined with the analysis of

¹ https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/box_out

² 道德 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tao_Te_Ching

³ 中醫 <https://nccih.nih.gov/health/whatiscam/chinesemed.htm>

⁴ 太极 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/T%27ai_chi_ch%27uan_philosophy

⁵ le - gender fluid

⁶ le - cis-gendered

⁷ As such the author regards the DSM new standard definitions as what they are: inherently sexist drivel.

⁸ See “Worlds in Collision,” I. Velikovsky (1950); contrary to claims he has not been debunked. In fact, a veritable thesis was written in response to Carl Sagan, and has itself not yet been responded to.

<http://robscholtemuseum.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Charles-Ginenthal-Carl-Sagan-Immanuel-Velikovsky.pdf>

⁹ [22]

HEMA¹⁰ and boxing will demonstrate several potential learning tools which may educate men on appropriate or inappropriate behavior. It may, in a side manner, educate women on their differences as well to aid in the raising of boys¹¹, prevention of domestic violence¹², enhancement of marriage circumstances¹³ (especially if they have become ‘toxic’¹⁴), and in fight prevention. To do this, there are some principles of the Taiji which must be illuminated as a general rule which always has individualized exceptions.

The Principles of the Taiji

The Taiji is an ancient concept however the symbol is a more recent inception. It may have existed previously, as per Perattian models of Birkeland Current cross-sections. However, the conceptualization has grown into a more mature categorization scheme which connects many disparate qualities or even hierarchies into a basic polar schemata. One such example is in the Huangdi Neijing¹⁵ which lists the “8 characteristics” in disease in medicine:

- Yang: Hot, Dry, Excessive
- Yin¹⁶: Cold, Wet, Deficient

Like the concept in biology of kingdoms and phylums, the lower genus and species do not define the upper, but contribute to its totality:

- Yang: male, upper, moving, stiff, dominant, powerful, illuminating, stubborn, angry, violent/aggressive
- Yin: female, below, still, flexible, strong, sturdy, dark or mystifying, yielding, docile, passive, nourishing

However, most westerners do not know the inter-penetrativeness of the definitions, and approach these concepts with the same rigidity as they would a biological classification. It is **never** unidimensional. There are 6 principles which guide the mutual aspects of the Polarity which prevent mere dualism from dominating the concept and the dharmic-law or binding Universal aspect of the inexplicable, ineffable “True Dao¹⁷”:

1. They are infinitely divisible and inseparable.¹⁸
2. They are mutually opposing (dualism)
3. They are mutually conforming or generating
4. They are mutually controlling (protagonism in resonance)
5. They are mutually destructive (antagonism in dissonance)
6. They are mutually consuming (isotopic imbalance, rarely 50/50)

Relative to the rest of life on Earth and definitely to the cosmos, humans are *all* 50/50 as a species, but are as a rule a yang species, preferring light, active creatures and spaces to dark ones. Yet, people do make pets of both yin and yang species regularly, despite trends; and they do live in yin places such as marshes. Relative to each other, men are naturally more yang¹⁹ (and have more Qi/Ch'i) and women are naturally yin

¹⁰ Historical European Martial Arts

¹¹ <https://divorcedmoms.com/post-divorce-mentoring-teen-boys>

¹² <https://www.thoughtco.com/low-self-esteem-linked-domestic-violence-3533790>

¹³ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/lcrp.12046>

¹⁴ In TCM this specifically means the non-transmutation, transportation, and rotation (sheng-generation) of yin > yang > yin

¹⁵ c. 400 BCE; legendarily a conversation taking place between the physician Qi Bo and the “Yellow Emperor” (a Saturnian motif), 4kya

¹⁶ An important maxim to remember: female is yin, but yin is not female.

¹⁷ Verse 1, Daodejing by Laoer/Laozi

¹⁸ This implies explicitly that one cannot exist without the other. So masculinity cannot be erased with various spectrum of strong and weak femininity.

¹⁹ As evidenced by the unbalanced nature of hypothyroidism, for example. Women are far more likely to be diagnosed with hypothyroidism than men.

(and have more Jing-essence)²⁰; again individuals may vary. Many women have stronger T-signals than men, and many men have more E-signals than women. But, as a rule, males have a slightly higher pulse rate in utero²¹, and require cooler temps, especially in puberty and in their 50s-60s, while females have lower pulse rates in utero, and require warming, except during the 40s-50s. Women as a rule have less Qi (energy-vapor) and more Jing (essence), but the body ceases jing loss at menopause²² to induce Qi preservation and their jing will therefore outlast most men who, without cultivation techniques²³, will continue to spend jing and Qi through ejaculation and effort until it suddenly runs vitally low, and they die younger (on average) than women²⁴. However, men are able to remain vital longer²⁵, if cultivated, and are muscularly stronger and more dominant in social²⁶ and sports^{27 28} settings. Women are, by and large more socially aware²⁹, docile, and accepting of the feelings and thoughts of others³⁰, with less desire to voice consternation, conflict, or create situations of social friction³¹. Feminism has altered this somewhat and female T-signals are on the rise³², while male T-signals are (worryingly^{33 34}) on the decline³⁵, which actually leads to hyper-masculinity (via the Taiji principles of mutual transformation and destruction).

There are some debates as to the culprit of these changes, but a general trend of masculinizing women and emasculating men is correlative, and cannot go unremarked upon³⁶. In contrast to the rising social equality of opportunity, physical differences and sexual characteristics have heightened in multiple large sample studies^{37 38}, leading to biological hypotheses surrounding paradox in the goals of equality^{39 40}.

Nevertheless, the focus of this paper is not rising female T-signals⁴¹ but instead the weak T-signals in men⁴² and their relationships to hyper-masculinity, and especially to the psychology of the cultural DNA hypothesis⁴³ vis-a-vis catastrophism.

²⁰ Average life expectancies for women always exceed those for men, worldwide.

²¹ <https://www.healthline.com/health/pregnancy/baby-heart-rate-predicting-gender#research>

²² All women undergo menopause, while not all men undergo manopause. Classically men undergo adrenopause, but in the modern era women are increasingly also undergoing adrenopause, and seeking hormone replacements not only for Estrogen but also warm adrenal hormones (yang).

²³ Taijiquan, Baguazhang, Qigong, Yoga, etc.

²⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23331196>

²⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26316253>

²⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6142169/>

²⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3761733/>

²⁸ Trans-women routinely break female records which within male sports they might actually underperform the average male athlete; this includes weight-lifting, track and field, bicycle, swimming, tennis, contact sports, boxing, etc.

²⁹

<https://www.kornferry.com/press/new-research-shows-women-are-better-at-using-soft-skills-crucial-for-effective-leadership>

³⁰ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244017725796>

³¹

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/the-brain-and-emotional-intelligence/201104/are-women-more-emotionally-intelligent-men>

³² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4653185/>

³³ https://www.health.harvard.edu/newsletter_article/Testosterone_aging_and_the_mind

³⁴ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/neilhowe/2017/10/02/youre-not-the-man-your-father-was/#45fb207f8b7f>

³⁵

<https://uk.reuters.com/article/health-testosterone-levels-dc/mens-testosterone-levels-declined-in-last-20-years-idUKKIM16976320061031>

³⁶ <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/real-men-dont-write-blogs/201803/feminizing-boys-we-masculinize-girls>

³⁷ <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0153857>

³⁸

<https://www.gu.se/english/research/news-detail//personality-differences-between-the-sexes-are-largest-in-the-most-gender-equal-countries.cid1587162>

³⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4839696/>

⁴⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_judkPi4_sY

⁴¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6555814/>

⁴² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2544367/>

⁴³ [2] and Velikovsky; D. Talbott

It is important to note that there is a linearization⁴⁴ of the Taiji which has some general use in this psychological study:

Extreme yin	“True Yin”	“True Yang”	Extreme Yang
Very Low IQ (men > women) 45	Low IQ (women > men) 46	High IQ (women > men) 47	V. High IQ (men > women) 48
Ultra violence	Passiveness	Aggressiveness	Assertiveness
Poverty	Dependency	Codependency ⁵⁰	Middle-class
			Rich
			Career-obsessed
			Cognitive Dominance ⁴⁹

The last is in reference to economic freedom or individuality only, and of course exceptions do exist. For example Charles Proteus Steinmetz was a genius and yet dependent upon General Electric for housing⁵¹. However, his disability⁵² may have influenced his decision, or perhaps a desire to maintain a strong influence upon the company even after retirement⁵³.

Similarly though there are very low IQ women with a tendency towards ultra violence⁵⁴, as a rule, double Y chromosomal males⁵⁵ with hyper T-signals are far more aggressive⁵⁶ and impetuous⁵⁷. This is also observed in pitbulls, for example⁵⁸. Dominant female jawlines demonstrating higher T-signal⁵⁹ do tend to correlate with aggressiveness, despite being within the “True Yin” arena. See Figure 2.

But it is *not* demonstrated that these women, such as MMA fighters, are well known for concurrent intellectual dominance, while multiple males in martial sports have demonstrated the ability to be very high IQ (with investments and media image), or just as likely, very low IQ⁶⁰ and even criminal⁶¹. This isn’t about splitting hairs between genders, it’s about understanding the *bookends* of male existence. Trusted males are capable of doing severe damage to spouses, children, families, businesses, nations, or even humanity, yet displaying often enormous fatal flaws and tendencies. Nevertheless, it is well known that even a bad boy or an evil man will attract female attachments and attentions⁶², which may even attempt to help them in their wickedness (such as robbery, murder, escape⁶³, enslaving women and children, arson, and genocide). We are not here,

⁴⁴ A sinusoid can be linearized but the sliding scale of the issue must be understood to reflect a circular reality!

⁴⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sex_differences_in_intelligence

⁴⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4199296/>

⁴⁷ <https://qz.com/441905/men-are-both-dumber-and-smarter-than-women/>

⁴⁸ All the highest rated chess and Go players in the world are male. The highest rated female in chess competition in history is 2735, which is a low score for a male grandmaster. The current top male grandmaster, Magnus Carlsen is over 3100. http://pogonina.com/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=815&Itemid=1

⁴⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RKSGA62SPIM>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/1967012>

⁵¹ <https://edisontechcenter.org/CharlesProteusSteinmetz.html>

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Charles_Proteus_Steinmetz

⁵³ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1646841>

⁵⁴ https://www.utdallas.edu/news/2012/5/1-17541_Study-Prison-Inmate-Intelligence-Influences-Miscon_article-wide.html

⁵⁵ <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/2/1/e000650>

⁵⁶ <http://www.scienceclarified.com/dispute/Vol-1/Are-XY-males-more-prone-to-aggressive-behavior-than-XY-males.html>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4525433/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2017/09/170927162032.htm>

⁵⁹ <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/under-the-influence/201209/testosterone-and-dominance>

⁶⁰ The author has conducted surveying of bankruptcy rates vs IQ, versus race; the results are staggeringly bad for african american males, who are less equipped to handle massive incomes, and have by far the largest average bankruptcies.

⁶¹ <https://www.chicagotribune.com/opinion/commentary/ct-nfl-sexual-assault-violence-20170502-story.html>

⁶² https://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2006-04/uol-mri042406.php

⁶³ <https://www.cnn.com/2015/07/28/us/new-york-prison-break-mitchell/index.html>

once again, to analyze the role of the female⁶⁴, we are merely discussing the masculine-hypermasculine axis, and the spectrum⁶⁵.

Figure 2 - Gabby Garcia (right) dominates another female competitor (both are biologically female) with increased T-signals and therefore mass. She won the bout in a brutal TKO one-sided victory, as expected from this snapshot of their dynamic. The UFC has not distinguished between females with higher T-signals.

Revisiting the Combat Motif

What is the **image** people have of combat? It is true that some people find violence too gruesome, abhorrent, and shy away from it. However, as the world continues with war and violence, and women engage in spectation, sport, and war theatre as well as planned strategic death (military scheming and intelligence), there is no denying or doubting the dominance of this aspect of human nature or natural reality.

While anyone on youtube/social media can observe some pacifistic and idealistic persons commenting anthropogenically about animal videos, most people by far accept the natural order (“Mother Nature”), despite its rapes and violence, as a thing of perpetual beauty *to be protected from humanity*. However, when humans behave following their own natural T and E signals, instinctually, there are cries (if that behavior is not done justly or with love) of cruelty, unfairness, inhumanity, and other shame-tactics which approximate a form of

⁶⁴ That is for a female writer to analyze.

⁶⁵ As a father of three boys (and a girl), the author has a particular interest in this topic as a developmental issue as well as survivability.

social justice. Multiple social experiments demonstrate the willingness of men and women to defend⁶⁶ (although not often enough⁶⁷) female victims of domestic violence⁶⁸, but never of male victims^{69 70}. In fact, more often than not, immediate male aggressions towards male victims who defend themselves arise, despite supposed “equality” measures in our laws. The female’s T-signal may even exceed the males⁷¹ but nevertheless the social norm is to berate the male and find humor⁷², while it is socially unconscionable to blame the female victim⁷³, regardless of potential circumstances or even outright lying⁷⁴. In some instances, proven male victims of false accusation have still been punished⁷⁵ by institutions such as Universities⁷⁶ or police⁷⁷, in order to protect the female-victim narrative^{78 79}.

Yet it is not proven that this is healthy for females or healthy demonstrative behavior of acceptable non-violent ethics for boys⁸⁰ and girls⁸¹. Instead, it may in fact *aggravate* hyper-masculinity^{82 83}.

How did this come to be? How did combat become **normalized** and yet natural male assertive-aggressiveness come to be labeled dangerous or ‘toxic’? It is truly, of course, very dangerous, and men are the first and most common recipient of violence (usually by other men)⁸⁴. Women, children, pets, and the elderly are also victims of hyper-masculinity stemming from men and increasingly women as well⁸⁵.

Looking to the Sumo analysis previously supplied by the author, it is clear that there is a long-standing tradition of dualistic combat⁸⁶. As it was generally accepted then, and is true now: men should not combat with women because while women are known to strike men in domestic situations, the damage caused is relatively minor (sans-weapon) while the damage a male strike can do to a female is substantial⁸⁷. So it was understood then, as it is now, that men should compete with men and women with women.

This however, did not change the motif or archetype of the warrior battlers. They were, in form and function, representatives of the cosmic planet-gods battling, going back first to Zeus vs. Kronos⁸⁸ and continuing downwards in time. It is not the author’s contention that the gods’ battles pre-existed mankind’s violence and that mankind was in a state of pacifism and perfect gender harmony. However two facts are known:

⁶⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xEZH6YSQvwA>, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GccCWo_eZdw, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZIHVANXh-yg>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5pL0JqWYr0E>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XNrWuZV3jjw>, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_TLd-GYXPHY

⁶⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y0arSz31DqI>

⁶⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30582724>

⁶⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4QFvEzIzQwg>

⁷⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X7vrl3JVIZ8>

⁷¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MNKclbrb_o4

⁷² https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uc6QxD2_yQw and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FgKsniZ4N9k>

⁷³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12321051>

⁷⁴ <https://www.washingtonexaminer.com/columbia-student-defamed-by-mattress-girl-is-suing>

⁷⁵ <https://nypost.com/2018/06/30/false-college-rape-allegation-destroyed-my-life-suit/>

⁷⁶ <https://abcnews.go.com/Politics/student-falsely-accused-sexual-harassment-denied-due-process/story?id=58592962>

⁷⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1TzTCWfiRew>

⁷⁸ <https://reason.com/2018/10/17/seneca-valley-mean-girls-false-sexual/>

⁷⁹ Some 10+ years ago the author tried to volunteer for the rape crisis hotline. Despite all statistics, it was just assumed a man answering the phone would be bad for rape victims, although many children and men are victims of female sexual assault.

⁸⁰ <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2010/sep/05/men-victims-domestic-violence>

⁸¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2968709/>

⁸² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w4cNe6rN11c>

⁸³ <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/04/12/us/domestic-violence-victims.html>

⁸⁴ <https://www.fbi.gov/news/pressrel/press-releases/fbi-releases-2017-crime-statistics>

⁸⁵ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20028091>

⁸⁶ Literally mano-e-mano; debate, boxing, wrestling, fencing, etc.

⁸⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2613333/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.greekboston.com/culture/mythology/kronos-zeus/>

1. War has a definite start date in human record⁸⁹, and it is post-breakup of the Saturnian system during the Archaic and Megalithic periods. It may have been for survival, but pillage economy definitely had a much more murderous danger to it than in the ancient past, after the Age of Ares began (Transition Period).
2. The Saturnian God-king was - worldwide- first and foremost a fertility God as well as a He-She conjunctive⁹⁰; sometimes a hermaphrodite, other times a king-Heaven-man who fertilizes and is born of his mother, marries his sister, and births his own son⁹¹. After the castration of Kronos⁹², Zeus the King of gods arises and Jupiter rules the sky unopposed for ~1500 years till Gilgamesh slays the Bull of Heaven⁹³. Gilgamesh is anthropomorphic Heracles, which is Hera's (now female Saturn) warrior, as Mars was of Saturn, not of Jupiter⁹⁴. Mars/Ares/Thor replaces the Jovian father king and the new generations re-interpret the motif as a father-son motif⁹⁵ where Ra/Ptah begets Osiris begets Horus. However, a foreign male-female god did threaten this relationship: Venus. For this Hera was repeatedly jealous of Zeus' consorts.⁹⁶

Venus' Archaic Origins and Changing Motif

We have learned from the Mayan-Aztec traditions that when Quetzlcoatl set himself on fire, from him burst his green heart and *it* became the Morning and Evening star.⁹⁷ This highly elliptical orbit created a "mischievous" appearance of the Bull of Heaven⁹⁸, known in Nordic tradition as Loki, a male-female shapeshifter⁹⁹. However, in the older middle east traditions, the bull was morphed into a bearded woman¹⁰⁰ and a cow¹⁰¹. The bearded woman was a warrior princess, whom the Romans called Diana and was in fact Athena¹⁰². It appears that at some point the comet tail of Venus passed around Jupiter and caused much cosmic lightning so that Zeus/Odin had to wrestle a cosmic snake or dragon¹⁰³. In the Nordic traditions, Loki turns into a female three times and births three monsters¹⁰⁴, one being a giant snake¹⁰⁵, who Thor (Mars) will wrestle with at the end of all things: Ragnarok¹⁰⁶. But the Greeks saw this event differently. Instead: Athena burst from the

⁸⁹ <https://www.haaretz.com/archaeology/.premium-fossils-offer-grim-proof-of-earliest-war-1.5257108>

⁹⁰ See "The Saturn Myth," D. Talbott

⁹¹ This all references to the proto-Saturn plasma double layer movement, and how the sheath functions to circulate the "four winds."

⁹² Literally the removal of Venus and Mars while they were exchanging plasma (creating a subjectively viewed cosmic phallus, reflected in Chinese glyphs), see [27] & [28]

⁹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bull_of_Heaven#Epic_of_Gilgamesh

⁹⁴ Heracles (/ˈhɛrəkliːz/ *HERR-ə-kleez*; Greek: Ἡρακλῆς, *Hēraklēs*, Glory/Pride of *Hēra*, "Hera")

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heracles>

⁹⁵ "the son of Zeus and Alcmene" Ibid.

⁹⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hera>

⁹⁷ <http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

⁹⁸ Ie - erratic motions relative to Earth perspective.

⁹⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Loki>

¹⁰⁰ Or Ishtar/Aphrodite http://people.duke.edu/~wj25/UC_Web_Site/myth/goddesses.html

¹⁰¹ Which is still revered as sacred today in India.

¹⁰² Sometimes the female goddess was called Aphrodite, but this is better identified with the moon on account of being Apollo's twin.

¹⁰³ <https://books.google.com/books?id=aOXQssPdIYC>

¹⁰⁴ <https://mythology.wikia.org/wiki/Loki>

¹⁰⁵ Who the Cherokee call Uktena and Norse called Jörmungandr and Greeks called Typhon.

<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Typhon>

¹⁰⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ragnar%C3%B6k>

forehead of Zeus (indeed probably passed through it, or partially¹⁰⁷), and came forth in battle array¹⁰⁸ and splendor, hot for battle exchange, which was joined by Ares who saved mankind from her rage.

In wiser traditions, the smaller planet was thought to be a suckling babe, or even a lover or consort. But in mountainous terrain where living conditions are often harder, such as Japan, Greece and northern Italy, this was seen as a battle indeed. The results of this battle were fairly clear: Mars **lost**. It lost mass in the northern hemisphere¹⁰⁹, received a great gashing scar (Valles Marinaris), lost its atmosphere¹¹⁰, perhaps the ability to nurture life, and only by the intervention of Zeus was Athena sent away, becoming instead the beautiful goddess. Venus has since slowed in rotation¹¹¹, dropped the presence of the still detectable plasma tail¹¹², and lost its highly elliptical orbit, and come near enough the Earth to becoming periodically entrained¹¹³. The two planets did however receive their respective places around the sun¹¹⁴, who was the likely actual intervening object (instead of Jupiter¹¹⁵).

Before Loki departs from the tales of Thor, there are many tales of tricks¹¹⁶ he performs upon Thor¹¹⁷, some evil indeed, and even causes the death of Baldr¹¹⁸ and banishment of Hodr-Hephaestus (Triton, perhaps¹¹⁹) Odin as the *adoptive* father is not always punitive towards Loki, whose monster-daughter Hel he is the *mother-father* of Hel has the grim aspect of being the bringer of doom and death. Indeed in India, Kali is so destructive that this era is still named the Kali Yuga.¹²⁰ Loki however, eventually leaves the story, and Thor becomes the mainstay of warrior power¹²¹. Later Ares/Thor approaches Earth bringing dust¹²² and destruction, casting thunderbolts and power, causing an age of war and pillaging¹²³ which can only be saved by institutionalized religion and yet not even then does this occur. The Berserker state¹²⁴ of the planet-god whom the Chinese said (as Houyi) shot the 9 suns¹²⁵ (leaving only the moon), was *worshipped* while the near death of all mankind blamed on the male-female goddess Venus, stuck as **blame**. In fact, the red tongue of Kali was from Mars¹²⁶ and not Venus, and yet Kali remains a female destroyer goddess while Vishnu is a male god of destruction and worshipped. To be fair to Hinduism/Buddhism, the *Green Tara* (an Aphrodite of sorts) remains a positive favorite¹²⁷.

¹⁰⁷ Aside from the disappeared goddess Eris, science has found:

<http://news.rice.edu/2019/08/14/young-jupiter-was-smacked-head-on-by-massive-newborn-planet-2/>

¹⁰⁸ Ie - smoldering clouds that are red-hot might appear like armor.

¹⁰⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

¹¹⁰ Venus clearly has way too much CO2 while Mars has far too little, which has baffled scientists until they created explanations which suit them. But none of them are proven.

¹¹¹ <https://www.universetoday.com/93494/is-venus-rotation-slowng-down/>

¹¹² <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/2013JA019164>

¹¹³ <https://www.sciencealert.com/the-celestial-dance-between-earth-and-venus-draws-a-stunning-pattern-through-space>

¹¹⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1405.0193>

¹¹⁵ Or perhaps a Thunderbolt stabilized charge in Venus and caused it to enter into the stable orbit it now holds.

¹¹⁶ <https://norse-mythology.net/loki-the-trickster-god-in-norse-mythology/>

¹¹⁷ <https://norse-mythology.org/gods-and-creatures/the-aesir-gods-and-goddesses/loki/>

¹¹⁸ <https://norse-mythology.org/tales/the-death-of-baldur/>

¹¹⁹ The only retrograde moon of its host, Neptune

¹²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kali_Yuga

¹²¹ Thursday is named for Thor, so that effectively 4 days of the week are named for Thunder Gods: Wednesday for Odin (Jupiter), Saturday for Saturn in Roman tradition, Tuesday for Tyr (Mars) and Thursday for Thor (Jupiter and Mars). By contrast Friday is named for Freya which was Saturn but became Venus.

¹²² The Chinese Ch'an Buddhists called the world of suffering not samsara (the three-fold world of the Buddhists) but the "Wheeling World of Red Dust" after the misery left in the era of the Greek Dark Ages (600s BCE).

<http://www.monksway.com/2016/08/03/red-dust/>

¹²³ Roughly Warring States Period <https://www.chinahighlights.com/travelguide/china-history/warring-states-period.htm>

¹²⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Berserker>

¹²⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Hou-Yi>

¹²⁶ Descending red dust which desertified the middle of the northern hemisphere.

¹²⁷ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tara_\(Buddhism\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tara_(Buddhism))

Duels and Ritualistic Male Combat as a Martian Archetype

The warrior path and chivalry, knights and mutual masculine admiration (and deadly hatred from rivalry thereby!) was the order of the world for the next 3,500 years¹²⁸. Why was this? What inherently causes men to seek out rivals to test themselves against? While female boxers and MMA exist, they came long after their male counterparts and the edge of fight evolution is still held by men, and pretty much universally held sacred. Many a priest enjoyed the fights of Catholic and Jewish boxers of the late 1800's and early 20th century, despite pacifistic vows. Shaolin warrior monks in China have strict vegan diets and Ch'an Buddhist vows, yet paradoxically enjoy martial training, weapons training (most of which have Saturnian and Jovian motifs), and did in fact engage in actual combat at rare times¹²⁹, as well as established sparring duels.

More famous than the Sumo combatants and gongfu, perhaps, are the Knights of Shining Armor who began ritualistic combat as wrestling sports in Greece¹³⁰ and Rome, then evolved into combat regiments and orders of schools for martial education¹³¹, which finally evolved into warrior classes in the west. This united with the feudal politico-economic systems to create Knighthood Nobility, and the ideals yet remained of *fair fighting* within a *defined boundary*. Though death was not preferred it was acceptable, even despite religious laws and anti-murder laws. To date over 500 men have died from boxing contests in the Scientific Period¹³²! As a martial artist, the author is both excited and mortified by this odd juxtaposition.

What have men thought about this since time immemorial? In general, men do not question the normalcy of combative ritual, from sport to boxing to even jousting or other knight combat. Men typically feel a rush a masculinity and a surge of competitiveness¹³³ in the presence of great athletes or combatants¹³⁴. It's both mental and physical, but not necessarily harmful in any way. In young men this can be used to instigate positive behavior, mimicry, and instill discipline¹³⁵.

After the age of Knights, HEMA entered an era of sword fighting and dueling¹³⁶. The sword is an ancient Saturnian motif for the weapon of the Thunder God¹³⁷. Following this it was firearms dueling which are cannons and make the 'thunder noise'¹³⁸. This is also a Saturnian or Jovian motif.

Figure 3 - boxing ring; credit: geezersboxing.co.uk

Immediately after this era came the era of western pugilistic boxing¹³⁹ (bare knuckle at first), in a square, roped off. Setting aside the similarity of the rope motif, as that may be purely coincidental to the sumo word for Yokozuna, the square is both conveniently shaped and a motif, as it is a raised platform. It is mirrored in China

¹²⁸ By Chinese reckoning

¹²⁹ <https://www.thoughtco.com/shaolin-monks-vs-japanese-pirates-195792>

¹³⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ancient_Greek_boxing

¹³¹ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3288082>

¹³² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_deaths_due_to_injuries_sustained_in_boxing

¹³³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5899443/>

¹³⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4554955/>

¹³⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3772577/>

¹³⁶ 1200s at the earliest; mostly Renaissance <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Duel>

¹³⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_magical_weapons

¹³⁸ <https://www.hup.harvard.edu/catalog.php?isbn=9780674737471>

¹³⁹ As early as the 1600s, but mostly the late 1800s. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bare-knuckle_boxing

Leitai platforms as well, often placed in the center of town¹⁴⁰. If it seems unreasonable that the ring being square (like the Heaven and Earth motif^{141 142}) and raised is a mere coincidence, consider the sumo dohyo as being the definite Saturnian cosmic hill, and also consider the MMA Octagon! See Figure 1 for an example of the “8 sided wheel” motif, which is also a worldwide archetype¹⁴³. Is this merely three coincidences or is it psychological DNA/cultural memory? It seems hardly capable of being anything else.

Loss, Emasculation, and Machismo

Men handle loss in various ways. Some pump themselves up, dust themselves off, and tell a different story. Others withdraw into themselves. Many others also become angry and destructive. That may not involve anything else than being competitive, but it's hard not to see it as violence, and too terribly often towards women and children¹⁴⁴.

What did it mean for humanity as a whole to see this battle of the gods, one the male archetype of the warrior god, and son of the Thunder Lord¹⁴⁵ - or simply The Lord - and the other the he-she goddess of war and death. This is a different god of death than Hades, lord of the Underworld¹⁴⁶. The lord of the Underworld was only master of the place of the dead, whereas the goddess of death wreaked the ultimate terror¹⁴⁷. Not everywhere was the god/dess seen as a goddess. For example, while in India the cow was worshiped, during the Exodus the Hebrews were so afraid they began to switch from the “orthodox” worship of Jehovah/Jove/Jupiter¹⁴⁸ to the golden calf¹⁴⁹.

So how did mankind - male and female - respond to this goddess' swath of destruction? It can be seen in the “mad witch” motif, which in Chinese gongfu has even the more explicit “mad witch with long white hair.”¹⁵⁰ She tends to be associated with black birds¹⁵¹ and sharp talons, which destroy masculine warriors but cannot destroy divine, purified ones¹⁵².

So how do men deal with loss, especially to women, nowadays? They respond with fear of being labeled effeminate, weak, etc. and by puffing up in their ego (chest, groin, and arms). In some cultures, where

¹⁴⁰ https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/entry/Lei_tai

¹⁴¹ “Heaven is round, Earth is square,” ~ a Daoist maxim

¹⁴²

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262701215_'On_Earth_as_it_is_in_Heaven_'_The_heavenly_sanctuary_motif_in_Hebrews_85_and_its_textual_connection_with_the_'shadowy_copy'_of_LXX_Exodus_2540

¹⁴³ [2] Appendix A

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.fatherly.com/health-science/toxic-masculinity-fake-male-insecurity/>

¹⁴⁵ As noted before, originally Mars was with Earth in the Saturnian system, and their tilts are all similar. However, As Horus was the avenging son of Osiris, but then later Jupiter became Horus the Hawk, it has been difficult for humanity to keep the story straight. Eventually Mars became the son of Jupiter, and Hera as a female goddess was deprived of Heracles in many a culture. To this day, most will tend to associate Mars/ manly qualities with Jupiter-Zeus', but in fact the qualities of warrior nature were derived of the original warrior goddess, who was seen as very jealous of Zeus and constantly interfering in his version of justice. She was noted to be a master manipulator and disfigurer of women. Probably a cultural motif based more upon anthropogenic behavior than upon gravity's effects on motion. However, given the number of cases of battling Valkyries, perhaps there is a missing aspect of a tug of war between Jupiter and Saturn which continued long after the castration (of Venus and Mars as testacles) of Saturn. One must remember these stories span thousands of years and often morph many times, especially as they mingle with other cultures and are adopted, and altered.

¹⁴⁶ Planet Uranus, not Pluto.

¹⁴⁷ Inana took the ME and the thunderbolt weapons from Marduk and used them, before they were taken back.

¹⁴⁸ J'ov'ah is clearly Jove for the Romans. However, the things most believers do not know is that Yahweh is a different Lord than El. When people say “amen” they of course send the prayers back to Amen-Ra, that is El. But the tetragrammaton is the Thunder God, Jupiter. Elohim was the original Lord of Hosts.

¹⁴⁹ Exodus 32:4

¹⁵⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_White_Haired_Witch_of_Lunar_Kingdom for example

¹⁵¹ <https://books.google.com/books/about/Wicked.html?id=bUOXuwEACAAJ>

¹⁵² “The Forbidden Kingdom,” (movie) for example

there is a long standing latent tradition of Venus and Mars worship, such as in Mexico, there also can be a tendency of machismo culture¹⁵³. This includes Japan, Italy, Scandinavia, etc. All of these cultures are renowned for their masculinity and hyper-masculinity. Vikings, for example, had an entire law that if a man was insulted as a homosexual or any form of “less than male” he had rights to challenge for a duel and claim blood¹⁵⁴. If they failed, however, they were unable to claim the right later in order to preserve cold-blooded revenge killings that weaken society¹⁵⁵.

What is machismo culture, if not the boisterous behavior and bravado which keeps away the fear of insecurity? It is not toxic perse (such an evaluation would be ethnocentric). It is however hyper-masculine, and in many cases it may ride the line of genuine or healthy behavior, and aggressive domineering¹⁵⁶.

Physics of the False Yin/False Yang dichotomy

The natural state of yin is strength. It is a different kind of strength than yang because it need not move to be strong and dominant. While yang is loud, aggressive, powerful, and stubborn, yin is still and centered, and ever-nourishing¹⁵⁷. While yang moves, and receives its domination through activity (such as male career obsession and workaholism), yin is naturally “re-charged” in its stillness. Consider, for example, criminality then, in terms of the yin/yang dichotomy. Its nature is dark, quiet, and beneath notice (generally speaking). But it cannot be considered true yin, it must be considered false yin. That means it is naturally still and strong. Meanwhile the police are dominant, in motion, and powerful. They are naturally forceful (male or female), demanding, and attracted to power and powerful weapons. But, unlike criminality which can last all day long, the police can only move and work so many hours a day before they are worn out. The Laozi says, “a strong wind does not blow all day.”¹⁵⁸

But consider when yin, true or false, displaces the stiff-necked position of yang, whether by insulting pride, or achieving victory over them (especially fairly, but in either case). The natural reaction is anger, movement, aggression, bravado, distraction, projection, or transposition. In some cases, the character, unable to see the self as whole and achieving - in very rare circumstances - will devolve into dark behaviors, such as addictions, criminality, etc. Whatever the result, very commonly false yang is the result. When a male loses their centrality due to a female, this is so remarkable it makes a common trope in media, stories, legends, myths, and fables.

Therefore is it shocking to see that this was the interpretation of the ancients of the day, when they observed the motions of Mars and especially when he came in a rage at the earth, scar-faced and tyrannical? A true berserker god, laying waste to all, in the final days of the conjunction, recorded as it is in glyph, story, and rock art: he came and vanquished and dominated all in a fury of motion and thunderous power. Then it was over and so was the age of the gods. Mankind abandoned the gods for messiahs and the lost Lord (and later for science, money, and technology).

Yin displacing yang is not merely an issue biologically (say in hypergonadotropism), or between the sexes (in men’s shrinking graduation rates and dropping IQ’s and T-signals), it is culturally remembered. In fact, the more the cultural understanding is violated, the less women respect men as a whole¹⁵⁹, and seek specific dominant men who fulfill the machismo behavior¹⁶⁰. In response, men who treat women (and other

¹⁵³ le - a “macho” man culture. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Machismo>

¹⁵⁴ <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/pwh/gayvik.asp>

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXCxNFxw6iq-Mh4uljYvufg>

¹⁵⁶ It is not a heterosexual act, either. Recently CNN anchor Don Lemon displayed machismo aggression in a bar, and nearly the same time co-host Chris Cuomo did as well, threatening to break a man’s legs and throw him down stairs for calling him “Fredo,” meaning “weak brother or son” of the Cuomo family. Don Lemon was sued for sexual harassment.

¹⁵⁷ http://www.pantherwebworks.com/i_ching/bk1h1-10.html#2

¹⁵⁸ Verse 23, Daodejing

¹⁵⁹ See recent Hollywood debacles of emasculation “Ghostbusters” (2016) and “Star Wars: The Last Jedi” (2017)

¹⁶⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/31016490>

people) more callously, even viciously, are rewarded for their dominance with support and excuses, while passive, pacific men are actually discarded¹⁶¹.

Wide growing numbers of involuntary celibates (called incels) take to the internet to complain that they are mistreated for being chivalrous and kind and sweet. Famously, Tupac Shakur is recorded in one instance expressing pain with a female telling him he was “too nice” and then later in his thuggish garb, saying that, “If you fuckin’ with a cool female that’s all good, but if you fuckin’ with a bitch you need to break her ass and shake her ass.”¹⁶² (sic, implying to get rid of her afterwards). Tupac famously went on to die from murder at a young age, after singing about a life of villainy and murder often with religious overtones.

Similarly, Snoop Dogg once led two women onto the MTV Music Awards stage wearing leashes and collars, led by another woman, showing clear dominance hierarchy related to money, masculinity, and power.¹⁶³ He was never punished and there has been no outcry from #metoo, instead he currently has a show on cable television. These may be very disturbing examples, but they are but a miniscule sample of hyper-masculinity bordering at the very start of aggression. There are numerous continuations both of the hyper-masculine and of the acceptance of it by men and women alike. Not all women are victims, and in fact a great many support this behavior and encourage it, for their own ends¹⁶⁴. So long as it is rewarded (and the author sees no reason why it would stop when in fact a hyper-male will be a rare alpha and in great demand in the increasingly beta male environment) then there is no reason to suspect it would stop. This is due to the physics and psychology of yin/yang in human nature. It is also due to the expectations in society, in our cultural DNA.

Consider a famous movie scene or series of scenes. In the Godfather, Sonny, the aggressive and violent eldest son of Don Corleone takes over the business. He yells at his sister and Carlo, for fighting. His mother stops him and says “don’t interfere” when the couple fight at the dinner table¹⁶⁵. Later, when his sister has been beaten, he chases down Carlo and beats him nearly to death¹⁶⁶. He says, “If you ever touch my sister again I’ll kill you.” He means it. The audience is meant to sympathize with Sonny. He is later murdered by being set up through this same scheme, and it is considered a tragedy for the family and the audience to witness. Michael, the younger brother kills Carlo (and everyone else), and he does so with such cold ruthlessness that the audience is satisfied and even awed. Yet the sister is unaware of the revenge killing until much later, because it was not for her to know, though she was the victim of two counts of domestic violence. She was not to be let into the male world of violence. There has been no general outcry about this, although it later plagues Michael’s marriage in parts 2 and 3.

It is difficult to even express to women how even in a situation of forced legal equality, the masculine (in a balanced state of true yang) cannot bring itself to be rough and uncouth (in public). But when the fear and insecurity take hold, and that is usually a problem within but can be instigated by a yin force from without, then false yang and hyper-masculinity can take hold publicly or privately. Both are masculine and natural. However, neither is - according to the male - for the female to understand. The moment of understanding, truly understanding it, is dangerous and often brutal. It may involve life-threatening violence or trauma. This is not an excuse, but it is a matter of understanding the principles of the Taiji: mutual destruction and opposition are not separate principles from mutual generation and control. They are part of a spectrum which is inter-connected by mutual behavior.

To break the cycle, or ‘box out’ the hyper-masculine, one must think *outside the box*. That doesn’t mean through the eyes of the feminine alone. Instead of attacking the masculine one needs to accept its motion and dominating movement, and then guide it to transformation into yin through wisdom. For men, this usually means a male related wisdom-cultivation path. For boxers that’s martial arts, but it could be religion or natural

¹⁶¹ The phenomenon of President Donald J. Trump is the most pertinent example of this.

¹⁶² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H7fgNpTxqw0>

¹⁶³ Rumors were that he was actually ‘pimping’ them.

¹⁶⁴ Take the support of Harvey Weinstein by famous actresses and Oprah.

¹⁶⁵ This, in the author’s opinion, accurately reflects the dominant belief among men and women in western society at large.

¹⁶⁶ Many do not know but that scene was improvised and actually James Conn really did beat the actor with a trash can!

endeavors like hiking, hunting, fishing, etc. It may even be video gaming or online¹⁶⁷. Motion is the key aspect of it. Stagnation will hinder the yang transformation and inter-penetration with yin, leading to failure to recycle and rejuvenate the energetic dynamics (social, physical, psychic, even fiscal)¹⁶⁸.

By introducing masculine spaces where the yang is not having to conform to an overt yin presence¹⁶⁹, the nascent internal yin - calm, soft, tender, gentle, etc. - will actually manifest in a natural hierarchy among the males. Alphas will lead betas and bring the group into a natural harmony, ready to receive powerful instruction. This is the “wise old Yoda” type archetype, which is prevalent in Asiatic and Aboriginal cultures, and which western cultures crave because of the deficiency of them in all the years of Dark Age hyper-masculinity.

However, third wave feminism, and to a large degree second wave feminism, has made such an emphasis upon the feminine that it’s become in most ways anti-masculine¹⁷⁰, and this is creating a trend of hyper-masculinity. This will probably not produce the desired results, but it will instead create a situation which is suitable for the hyper-aggressive masculine male. His T-signals will be considerably in demand and pay highly. Manipulative and narcissistic behaviors which mask character flaws to emphasize salesman-like charm and lying will be rewarded extra, while the honest, strong silent-type will be put down as “undesirable.” Females will flock to the “wrong guy” over and over¹⁷¹, using sex to try to “litmus test” numerous potential partners, seeking in vain to find the kind of masculinity which can quell false yin without abusing it, and thus converting it to true yin. But that search will be - as indicated by the Cinderella culture¹⁷² - much in vain.

Rather, we should seek to understand all of these behaviors are not merely the physics of yin and yang, and the biology of hormones and pheromones, but actually rooted in our psyche and understanding of how the gods behaved, and therefore what is acceptable socially. It is Biblical as well. When women step out of line historically, they may be acceptably stoned or put to death. In the Quran, it is explicitly stated when the conditions are acceptable for this¹⁷³. There are imams present in the United States and Europe which teach the doctrine of “miswak,”¹⁷⁴ that is slapping around the wife without outright beating her, to engender respect¹⁷⁵. These ways and beliefs all stem from a more ancient time which was living under direct observation of the behavior of **mere spheres**, powerful as they were, which were anthropogenically understood as living beings. So much so that the majority of the population alive today still believes in angels, giants, demons, and aliens, even as we exist in the Scientific Period!¹⁷⁶ This isn’t a single culture, it is fairly ubiquitous throughout the world, albeit in varying degrees and forms. The anatomy of the male psyche is what it is, and the cultural memory and mythic motifs are what they are. If one says “they are undesirable” I would tend to agree, except again the emphasis on *emasculatation as a solution does not respect the physics*, and instead promotes hyper-masculinity both in the short and long term. Rather, by dissecting and understanding masculinity and not casting it away in the hope of creating equality via one pole promotion, perhaps there is an understanding which can box out the behavior of hyper-masculinity via the masculine true yang (and its inherently centered true yin within the person).

Boxing, Dominance, Athleticism, and Self-confidence.

There is no denying that men operate primarily from a place of a dominance hierarchy. This is inherently natural to men. To try to stamp this out would be an impossible and an immoral task. Men who see

¹⁶⁷ <https://www.polygon.com/2014/9/12/6141515/do-violent-video-games-actually-reduce-real-world-crime>

¹⁶⁸ This is known as the “Mysterious pivot” (lingshu) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lingshu_Jing

¹⁶⁹ Such as forcing boy scout troops to accept girls.

¹⁷⁰ <https://fcpp.org/2018/07/11/toxic-feminism/>

¹⁷¹ <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/lifetime-connections/201605/stop-dating-the-wrong-person>

¹⁷² <http://www.collegehumor.com/video/6948903/tinderella-a-modern-fairy-tale>

¹⁷³ 6:60:79, 17:4192, 17:4206 and 4209

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2979/fsr.2010.26.2.11>

¹⁷⁵ 4:34 and 38:44

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/poll-nearly-8-in-10-americans-believe-in-angels/>

the world primarily from a competitive standpoint, whether for good or ill, for social or selfish benefit, would become listless, depressed, and take to crime and other underhanded activities. Many would become domestic and child abusers, expressing their frustrations on the weak and powerless, disenfranchised, etc. This, therefore, does not solve the issue. For third wave feminism to demand men to change biologically¹⁷⁷, overnight, is tantamount to sexism and discrimination.¹⁷⁸ Men can no more change their natural T-signals as children and boys, then as adolescents or finally adults, than an African American can help from being born with more melanin, or a girl being born without a penis, or a blind person born unable to see. Discrimination of this sort, founded in postmodernist deconstructionism¹⁷⁹ is inherently brutal in that it engenders new, previously unknown extremes, many of which do not follow natural curvatures (such as creating pre-pubescent trans children¹⁸⁰, etc.)

But neither is it acceptable to always allow masculinity to flourish until it flowers over into hyper-masculine situations, such as college date rape at fraternities and dorms, or gang violence and fighting, or board-room political assassination and isolating individuals whether for sexism or male-to-male rivalry reasons. Ever more frequently, homosexual hyper-masculinity has become commonly involved in sexual aggression and predation¹⁸¹, not only of homosexual males and children but of heterosexual males. The T-signal can, and will, increase in potentially exponential ways in certain situations, when conditions appear and not enough yin is present to decrease the yang. How can one predict when an elephant will go into musth?¹⁸² Certain animals where the hyper-masculinity is so strong requires separation, such as keeping ungelded bulls and stallions in separate paddocks away from males and females alike. But that is not an option with humanity, not even with double-Y chromosome males.

Instead, the author advocates that we teach about masculinity and instead of “swatting the hand” explain when “boys will be boys” becomes predatory, so that other males will moderate the signal in the room or situation. That will not work in all cases, and certain situations will become “toxic” in which case actually promoting hyper-masculinity will be important to creating peace defenders in a period (lengthy or short) of ‘war.’ Good men need to be empowered to achieve hyper-masculine states to dominate against men committing evil crimes. When they are afraid, because of backlash in career, media, or work, then you get situations such as the Terry Crews sexual assault¹⁸³ where inordinately large and dominant males feel disempowered to even defend themselves **in the situation**.

Consider also the rise in rates of “toxic” male behavior such as the “knock-out game”¹⁸⁴... can it really be the role of society to convince men that they should not immediately, aggressively defend females or gay partners, in the event of imminent self-defense situations? Also why should they not defend men being victimized by women engaging in false yin activities like haranguing (verbal abuse) and slapping men who are clearly indicating they don’t want to fight.¹⁸⁵

This is why the author promotes- despite the oddity of the events and the obscure origins related to terrible times in human history with antiquated and superstitious thinking - the use of boxing and martial arts to

¹⁷⁷ Most readily, in the workplace, where they use sexual markers and indicators in dress and attractive cosmetics, but expect men to show no interest. This is obviously misandrist because these products are designed for the explicit and inherent sexual attraction factor they add.

¹⁷⁸ <https://www.quora.com/What-are-disadvantages-of-being-male-as-opposed-to-female>

¹⁷⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Postmodernism>

¹⁸⁰ Experiments regarding trans children have often had disastrous, dangerous, and tragic results
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SLFGMWoQaCU>

¹⁸¹ Consider the case of Kevin Spacey

¹⁸² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/musth>

¹⁸³ Terry Crews is a very large African American male actor, who testified in Congress about being victimized by a homosexual male of power in Hollywood. He did not fight back, and many people were confused as to why. He explained it as a fear of losing position and status. However, more accurate would be to say he didn’t feel he had agency. Victims - male or female, adult or child, majority or minority, should have agency to defend themselves.

¹⁸⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knockout_game

¹⁸⁵ <https://www.dailymotion.com/video/x2loytf>

teaching youth, and particularly males, how to deal with their masculine energy. Firstly, it is better to transform yang into yin (and back to yang) than to quell it and create a false yang and dangerous inward energy. Secondly, it improves the relationship of men over a strata of ages from senior to juvenile. In some instances it provides healthy father-daughter relationships which produce *highly empowered girls*^{186 187 188} or just generally improves family situations. Third, it fosters the techniques of self-defense and survival skills which are still relevant in society today.

Finally but not unimportantly it provides an outlet for that cultural DNA signature which seeks to express itself over and over again in hero films¹⁸⁹, religious studies, media¹⁹⁰, and of course competitive sports and combat. The more that the situation is expressed, the more likely the underlying pathology of unnatural yin/yang disharmony between males and females can be resolved. But it is also incredibly important to set about it in a healthy masculine way, and to not over-encourage hyper-masculinity. It must be taught to be a rarely used resource, for both personal and social health reasons. Most women would agree they will feel safer if men reserve hyper-masculinity to interpersonal contests between males and not themselves being challenged.¹⁹¹

By encouraging the T-signals in men, we can as a society address the dropping T-signals and rising depression and dropout rates¹⁹², as well as improve the athleticism (and thereby improve national defense for any nation), sports quality (and avoid cheaters¹⁹³), and of course, teach boys how to be men, rather than punish them for naturally being men *after* they have failed a social litmus test which is based on ancient codes and modern technicalities.

Commercials such as the one Gillette produced¹⁹⁴ do not do this, and the results were obvious: an \$8 billion loss¹⁹⁵. This is because the message won't reach men when coming from that insincere and sexist place that is so prevalent in third and now fourth wave feminism¹⁹⁶. It will only create more and more hyper-masculinity which is unrepentantly chauvinist, violent, and aggressive in all spheres. Instead we should promote health masculinity in programming, comic books¹⁹⁷, cartoons, news coverage, schools, and sports. Perhaps even politics will be able to right itself. The issue of dominance between males, and males and females could naturally resolve itself instead of leading to a cultural civil war, or an actual civil war. Certainly it should help to curb homegrown and religious extremist terrorism and fundamentalism, which threatens and egalitarian way of life, and liberty, and justice for all.

Final Thoughts

Men have created the most of everything: the most problems, and by far the most solutions, including almost all of modern living. But it can be said to have been a partnership in a struggle against nature and human nature. Life on this planet has not been easy and lifespans and literacy not long acquired. Some had access to the life sciences and improved health opportunities, and those who did had reputedly long lives and

¹⁸⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mhZ51wYSpxc>

¹⁸⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aEjQQB9BKWA>

¹⁸⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kxy_DWdBoCk

¹⁸⁹ "Avengers" et al.

¹⁹⁰ "Star Wars" et al.

¹⁹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LOD-nmLZAU> and https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sMqr_eMvCul

¹⁹² <https://www.theatlantic.com/education/archive/2017/08/why-men-are-the-new-college-minority/536103/>

¹⁹³ Trans-women (men competing in female sports) are effectively doping, and they know it. ^

¹⁹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=koPmuEyP3a0>

¹⁹⁵ <https://pjmedia.com/trending/gillette-loses-billions-by-shaming-men/>

¹⁹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fourth-wave_feminism

¹⁹⁷ Telling men they aren't "worthy" as the female Thor arc (and upcoming movie) did is likely only going to inflame the situation, and aside from being incredibly sexist, it was also a form of religious ethnocentric hate. It only further inflames hyper-masculine subcultures such as right wing Scandinavian heavy metal and white supremacy nationalism.

developed language and writing, and shared the mythic histories. But for the most part it has been a partnership against struggle. For most of recorded human history the average person has survived on the equivalent of less than \$2 a day. There was basically no economy to speak of, save pillage economy, or city-state war and simple merchant class small business. Feudalism was expensive, and most money went to arms.

Yet, to speak now, realistically, about masculinity, within 50 years of the start of postmodernism (and despite the rise in average incomes since the 1800s to be the greatest in the world in the USA), is considered by the mainstream of academia and media some kind of attack upon femininity. It is not. But in order to discuss real male problems and issues, one must set aside biases in both directions, and all political and racial directions, in order to see through to the axis of the issue. In this case, what the myths have revealed about the origins of male insecurity and hypermasculine dominance, as well as about the properties of the yin/yang axis itself, are very useful for understanding issues like domestic violence (in either direction), workplace harassment, sports disparity, and war.

It is very unfruitful for deconstructionists to pretend that these issues will be solved with a one-axis form of egalitarianism, because as any mathematician will attest one cannot solve an equation by unbalancing it to one side and not addressing the other side. The fact is that the most recent forms of feminism have only heightened tensions by making assertions about masculinity and the world of relating to and with men in public, which are untrue and generally unimportant in terms of the resolving of the issue. All the statistics show that fathers are the key to balanced, successful, well-adjusted children. Criminality, poverty, and mental disease are all related to the absence of fathers in the lives of children. And yet there is very little in the movement of discussion of men's own rights and father rights. That is partially because of biology (people laugh at abused men because it seems backwards, and people laugh out of nervousness), and partly because of social narrative (the woman is always the victim and "you must believe her"). One thing is for sure, based on biology, physics, and psychology: empowering masculine males to teach boys how to be properly masculine, is the surest way to decrease violence, criminality, war and enhance economy, security, technology, etc.

There is a common misconception amongst social deconstructionists, that to enhance the position of one group, whose disenfranchisement may be real or perceived, is to rob the real or perceived group - particularly heterosexual white males, and Christians - of their position. Mathematically this is not correct, as it was long ago proved that a rising tide lifts all ships in cooperation. Competition is healthy. But actually mankind has been favored through male biology. Neither gender has been perfect, just as nobody is perfect. There have been some high profile cases of abuse, most of them by males, and most of the publicised victims female. But neither case is 100%. Women have abused other women and men, and men have been the victims of men. Nothing is perfect, but perhaps through understanding and observation - and recollection of our shared miserable pasts - we can start to understand one another, too. If anything is true, it is that understanding and compassion are greater virtues than ignorance and bigotry are vices. But only if they are empowered by mutual faith, trust, and open willingness.

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